

A facile microwave assisted one-pot strategy for the synthesis of bis-hexahydroquinazolin-5(6H)-ones

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Abstract : A facile microwave assisted one-pot synthesis of novel bis-hexahydroquinazolin-5(6H)-ones (**7a-j**) has been devised by the cyclocondensation of cyclic enaminones (**6a-b**) with diamines and formaldehyde. The structures of the products have been established with the help of their spectral and analytical data as 3,3'-(alkanedyl/arenedyl)bis-1-benzyl-7,7-dimethyl-1,2,3,4,7,8-hexahydroquinazolin-5(6H)-ones and 3,3'-(alkanedyl/arenedyl)bis-1-benzyl-1,2,3,4,7,8-hexahydroquinazolin-5(6H)-ones.

Keywords : Bis-hexahydroquinazolin-5(6H)-ones, hexahydroquinazolin-5(6H)-ones, enaminones, cyclocondensation, diamines, formaldehyde.

Introduction

Fused pyrimidine ring systems are well known to possess important medicinal¹, antimalarial² and other biological properties³. In view of the biological importance of 1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8-octahydroquinazolin-2,5-diones as calcium antagonist^{4,5} and potential antibacterials^{6,7}, we have recently reported the synthesis of 1-phenyl-3-(alkyl/aralkyl/aryl)-5-oxo-1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8-octahydroquinazolines and 1-phenyl-3-(alkyl/aralkyl/aryl)-7,7-dimethyl-5-oxo-1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8-octahydroquinazolines (**1**)⁸, 1-benzyl-3-(alkyl/aralkyl/aryl)-5-oxo-1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8-octahydroquinazolines and 1-benzyl-3-(alkyl/aralkyl/aryl)-7,7-dimethyl-5-oxo-1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8-octahydroquinazolines (**2**)⁸, bis-1-phenylhexahydroquinazolin-5(6H)-ones (**3**)⁹, 1-methyl-3-(alkyl/aralkyl/aryl)-5-oxo-1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8-octahydroquinazolines and 1-methyl-3-(alkyl/aralkyl/aryl)-7,7-dimethyl-5-oxo-1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8-octahydroquinazolin (**4**)¹⁰ and bis-1-methylhexahydroquinazolin-5(6H)-ones (**5**)¹⁰.

In continuation of our studies on the synthesis of octahydroquinazolines, we herein wish to report the synthesis of hitherto unreported bis-octahydroquinazolines bearing benzyl group in position 1 of the ring under microwave irradiation (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

Results and discussion

Thus when a mixture of 3-benzylamino-7,7-dimethyl-cyclohex-2-en-1-one (**6a**), ethylenediamine and formaldehyde (2 : 1 : 4) in methanol was subjected to MWI, work-up of the reaction mixture followed by chromatographic purification yielded to a solid in 65% yield, which was characterized as 3,3'-(ethane-1,2-diyl)bis(1-benzyl-7,7-dimethyl-1,2,3,4,7,8-hexahydroquinazolin-5(6H)-one (**7a**) with the help of spectral and analytical data. The reaction was found to be general with other diamines and with corresponding enaminones (**6a-b**) to give the respective **7a-j** in 39-78% overall yields. The structures of the rest of the compounds were also established on the basis of spectral

Table 1. Synthesis of bis-quinazolines (7a-j)

Entry	Enaminones	Conditions	Bis-quinazolines
1	7a		
2	6a	H ₂ N-(CH ₂) ₃ -NH ₂ , CH ₂ O/ MeOH/180 W 3 min	7b
3	6a	H ₂ N-(CH ₂) ₄ -NH ₂ , CH ₂ O/ MeOH/180 W 3 min	7c
4	6a	H ₂ N-C ₆ H ₄ -NH ₂ , CH ₂ O/ MeOH/450 W 3 min	7d
5	6a	H ₂ N-(C ₆ H ₄) ₂ -NH ₂ , CH ₂ O/ MeOH/450 W 4 min	7e
6	7f		
7	6b	H ₂ N-(CH ₂) ₃ -NH ₂ , CH ₂ O/ MeOH/450 W 5 min	7g
8	6b	H ₂ N-(CH ₂) ₄ -NH ₂ , CH ₂ O/ MeOH/450 W 5 min	7h
9	6b	H ₂ N-C ₆ H ₄ -NH ₂ , CH ₂ O/ MeOH/450 W 5 min	7i
10	6b	H ₂ N-(C ₆ H ₄) ₂ -NH ₂ , CH ₂ O/ MeOH/450 W 4 min	7j

and analytical data. Thus, the infrared spectra of **7a-j** showed strong peaks in the range of 1513 to 1670 cm⁻¹ due to highly delocalized double bonds and carbonyl group stretching frequencies of enaminone functionalities. In the ¹H NMR spectra of **7a** and **7f** the NCH₂ protons of ethylene chain appeared as singlets at 2.61 and 2.62 ppm respectively whereas the NCH₂ protons of propylene chain **7b** and **7g** appeared as multiplets near 2.45 ppm and 2.29 ppm and that of C₂ protons of propylene chain appeared as multiplets around 1.25 and 1.92 ppm respectively. Likewise in **7c** and **7h** protons at C₁ and C₂ of butylene chain appeared as multiplets between 2.32–2.81 and 1.38–1.96 ppm respectively. The protons at C₂ and C₄ of quinazoline ring resonated in the range of 4.44–4.47 and

3.92–4.44 ppm respectively. The methyl protons at C₇ of quinazoline ring in **7a-e** appeared as singlets in the range of 1.04–1.06 ppm. The protons at C₇ of quinazoline ring in **7f-j** appeared as multiplets in the range of 1.58–1.96 ppm. The aromatic protons resonated in their usual range of 6.84–7.39 ppm.

Experimental

Melting points were recorded by open capillary method and are uncorrected. The IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 983 spectrometer. High-resolution ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR (300 MHz) spectra were recorded on Bruker ACF-300 spectrometer. The chemical shift (δ ppm) and coupling constants (Hz) are reported in standard fashion

with reference to TMS as internal reference. FAB-Mass spectra (MS) were measured on Jeol 3SX 102/DA-6000 using Argon as the FAB gas and *m*-nitrobenzyl alcohol as the matrix. Elemental analysis was performed on a Vario-EL-III instrument. Microwave irradiation was carried out in a domestic MW oven (Samsung CE 27 33G) operating at 2450 MHz. Enaminones **6a** and **6b** were synthesized by our reported procedure¹¹.

General procedure : A mixture of diamine (0.5 mmol) and formaldehyde (2 mmol, 40% solution) in 1.5 mL methanol was shaken at room temperature for 5 min. To this a solution of enaminones **6** (1 mmol) in 5–6 mL methanol was added and the resulting mixture was irradiated in a domestic microwave oven for 2–5 min. After the completion of the reaction (monitored by tlc), methanol was removed under reduced pressure to give a gum, which was subjected to column chromatography (silica gel, ethylacetate) to isolate **7a–j** in 39–78% yields. All these products gave satisfactory analytical and spectral data.

3,3'-(Ethane-1,2-diyl)bis-1-benzyl-7,7-dimethyl-1,2,3,4,7,8-hexahydroquinazoline-5(6H)-one (7a) : It was obtained as pale yellow solid in 65% yield; m.p. 78 °C; IR (KBr) : 1560, 1600 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 1.05 (12H, s), 2.19 (4H, s), 2.31 (4H, s), 2.61 (4H, s), 3.55 (4H, s), 4.02 (4H, s), 4.43 (4H, s), 7.16–7.39 (10H, m); MS : *m/z* 567.4 (MH⁺).

3,3'-(Propane-1,3-diyl)bis-1-benzyl-7,7-dimethyl-1,2,3,4,7,8-hexahydroquinazoline-5(6H)-one (7b) : It was obtained as pale yellow gum in 45% yield; IR (KBr) : 1524, 1602 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 1.05 (12H, s), 1.25–1.28 (2H, m), 2.20 (4H, s), 2.31 (4H, s), 2.45–2.49 (4H, m), 3.51 (4H, s), 3.92 (4H, s), 4.44 (4H, s), 7.18–7.37 (10H, m); MS : *m/z* 581.4 (MH⁺).

3,3'-(Butane-1,4-diyl)bis-1-benzyl-7,7-dimethyl-1,2,3,4,7,8-hexahydroquinazoline-5(6H)-one (7c) : It was obtained as pale yellow solid in 78% yield; m.p. 87 °C; IR (KBr) : 1517, 1600 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 1.05 (12H, s), 1.38–1.40 (4H, m), 2.20 (4H, s), 2.31 (4H, s), 2.32–2.40 (4H, m), 3.52 (4H, s), 3.94 (4H, s), 4.44 (4H, s), 7.18–7.37 (10H, m); MS : *m/z* 595.4 (MH⁺).

3,3'-(1,4-Phenylene)bis-1-benzyl-7,7-dimethyl-1,2,3,4,7,8-hexahydroquinazoline-5(6H)-one (7d) : It was obtained as pale yellow solid in 52% yield; m.p. 170 °C; IR (KBr) : 1513, 1560 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 1.04

(12H, s), 2.23 (4H, s), 2.26 (4H, s), 4.16 (4H, s), 4.44 (4H, s), 4.56 (4H, s), 4.65 (4H, s), 7.26–7.28 (14H, m); MS : *m/z* 615.4 (MH⁺).

3,3'-(Biphenyl-4,4'-diyl)bis-1-benzyl-7,7-dimethyl-1,2,3,4,7,8-hexahydroquinazoline-5(6H)-one (7e) : It was obtained as pale yellow solid in 65% yield; m.p. 185 °C; IR (KBr) : 1545, 1608 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 1.06 (12H, s), 2.21 (4H, s), 2.50 (4H, s), 3.52 (4H, s), 3.93 (4H, s), 4.45 (4H, s), 7.21–7.38 (18H, m); MS : *m/z* 691.4 (MH⁺).

3,3'-(Ethane-1,2-diyl)bis-1-benzyl-1,2,3,4,7,8-hexahydroquinazoline-5(6H)-one (7f) : It was obtained as pale yellow gum in 42% yield; IR (KBr) : 1560, 1608 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 1.92–1.96 (4H, m), 2.29–2.32 (4H, m), 2.44–2.47 (4H, m), 2.62 (4H, s), 3.52 (4H, s), 3.98 (4H, s), 4.43 (4H, s), 7.15–7.37 (10H, m); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 21.51, 25.88, 29.68, 35.68, 47.64, 52.38, 70.26, 77.03, 103.76, 126.32, 129.07, 136.78, 159.01, 193.85; MS : *m/z* 511.3 (MH⁺).

3,3'-(Propane-1,3-diyl)bis-1-benzyl-1,2,3,4,7,8-hexahydroquinazoline-5(6H)-one (7g) : It was obtained as pale yellow gum in 39% yield; IR (KBr) : 1560, 1659 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 1.58–1.63 (4H, m), 1.92–1.95 (4H, m), 2.13–2.16 (2H, m), 2.29–2.32 (4H, m), 2.46 (4H, s), 3.35 (4H, s), 3.88 (4H, s), 4.44 (4H, s), 7.17–7.37 (10H, m); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 21.51, 25.76, 30.94, 35.67, 48.30, 51.55, 69.50, 77.04, 104.37, 126.31, 127.78, 129.05, 136.82, 158.83, 193.75; MS : *m/z* 525.4 (MH⁺).

3,3'-(Butane-1,4-diyl)bis-1-benzyl-1,2,3,4,7,8-hexahydroquinazoline-5(6H)-one (7h) : It was obtained as pale yellow gum in 45% yield; IR (KBr) : 1552, 1601, 1670 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 1.68–1.69 (4H, m), 1.94–1.96 (4H, m), 2.11 (4H, s), 2.29 (4H, s), 2.78–2.81 (4H, m), 3.44–3.48 (4H, m), 3.90 (4H, s), 4.44 (4H, s), 7.17–7.37 (10H, m); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 21.53, 25.70, 30.94, 35.69, 47.95, 52.31, 69.65, 77.04, 104.30, 126.35, 127.78, 129.03, 136.85, 158.84, 193.79; MS : *m/z* 539.7 (MH⁺).

3,3'-(1,4-Phenylene)bis-1-benzyl-1,2,3,4,7,8-hexahydroquinazoline-5(6H)-one (7i) : It was obtained as pale yellow gum in 52% yield; IR (KBr) : 1527, 1605 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 1.93–1.95 (4H, m), 2.34–2.37 (4H, m), 2.42–2.44 (4H, m), 4.09 (4H, s), 4.47

(4H, s), 4.52 (4H, s), 6.96–7.37 (4H, m); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 21.49, 25.87, 29.70, 35.71, 46.08, 52.25, 68.41, 77.02, 105.06, 119.12, 126.21, 127.73, 129.01, 136.43, 159.62, 193.56; MS : *m/z* 559.4 (MH⁺).

3,3'-(Biphenyl-4,4'-diyl)bis-1-benzyl-1,2,3,4,7,8-hexahydroquinazoline-5(6H)-one (7j) : It was obtained as pale yellow gum in 48% yield; IR (KBr) : 1547, 1608 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 1.76–1.89 (4H, m), 2.29–2.32 (4H, m), 2.38–2.39 (4H, m), 4.19 (4H, s), 4.44 (4H, s), 4.58 (4H, s), 6.84–7.39 (18H, m); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 21.48, 25.89, 29.70, 35.71, 45.52, 52.26, 67.56, 77.03, 105.03, 117.82, 126.28, 127.23, 129.04, 136.41, 147.32, 159.70, 193.66; MS : *m/z* 635.8 (MH⁺).

Conclusion :

This paper describes an efficient, simple, fast and environment-friendly methodology for synthesizing hitherto unreported bis-octahydroquinazolines from easily accessible starting materials. The methodology reported herein is an example of multi-component reactions (MCRs).

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